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INSTINCT

D1.2

Channel, Propagation, and Sensing Models

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents key advancements in channel, propagation, and sensing models for integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) systems. This is often also called integrated communication and sensing (ICAS) or joint communications and sensing (JCAS) in the literature. One particular focus area is the reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) as an enabling technology. The need for ISAC comes from growing demand for intelligent, adaptive, and secure wireless networks in the context of 6G and beyond. RIS offers a transformative approach to shaping the wireless channels and it enables enhanced communication performance and environmental awareness through programmable electromagnetic surfaces. ISAC, on the other hand, expands the communications networks into sensing networks. This benefits both communications and sensing via sensing giving tools for prediction and communications enabling massive sensing.

The research herein combines experimental, theoretical, and simulation-based works. Experimentally, a beamforming control algorithm for RISs was developed and validated with real measurements. The RIS is also shown to improve system performance and security as well. A data header structure was proposed that enables sensing without compromising communications performance.

Theoretically, a network theory -based RIS model is given on top of novel mutual coupling-aware RIS channel models and blockage models. Furthermore, it is shown that RISs can enhance ISAC systems significantly. Additionally, a GPU-accelerated ray tracing tool was employed to simulate realistic propagation environments, supporting the evaluation of RIS and ISAC performance in complex urban scenarios.

This deliverable plays an important role in the INSTINCT project by providing the modeling tools and experimental insights necessary for designing and optimizing RIS-assisted ISAC systems. This deliverable is also the main results of INSTINCT task 1.2. The findings in this report support the broader project goals of intelligent ISAC wireless networks and sets the stage for future work on system integration, performance evaluation, and real-world deployment.

Keywords

ISAC, ICAS, JCAS, RIS, sensing, reconfigurable environments, RIS models, ISAC models, channel modeling, blockage, ray tracing.

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1 Introduction

The evolution of wireless communication systems towards sixth generation systems (6G) is increasingly driven by the need for enhanced spectral efficiency, energy efficiency, and sustainability. As we approach the first 6G implementations, the integration of communication and sensing functionalities has emerged as a promising technology. This is known as integrated sensing and communications (ISAC), or often integrated communication and sensing (ICAS) or joint communications and sensing (JCAS) in literature. The ISAC systems aim to combine data transmission and sensing that enables advantages for both sensing and communications. ISAC can help with system optimization, prediction, and channel estimation. On the other hand, vast networks allow large amounts of sensing information as a side product of communication. Within this context, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) have gained prominence as an enabler of ISAC, offering dynamic control over electromagnetic wave propagation through programmable and simple network devices.

This report focuses on the development and evaluation of channel, propagation, and sensing models tailored for ISAC systems and RIS-assisted ISAC systems. The work is structured around both experimental and theoretical investigations, aiming to look at the problem from viewpoints of conceptual models and practical implementations. The experimental works introduce a pixel-by-pixel (PBP) beamforming control algorithm for RIS, designed to optimize far-field radiation patterns for enhanced localization and communication. The algorithm is validated through a series of measurements using a feedback system and motorized RIS setup. This shows its ability to generate targeted beamwidths with varying degrees of accuracy across different frequencies and directions.

This report also looks at the integration of RIS into physical layer security setups, demonstrating its potential to increase secret key generation (SKG) rates by introducing controlled randomness into the channel. Experimental setups using USRP devices validate the effectiveness of RIS in enhancing channel reciprocity and entropy, particularly in static environments where SKG rates are typically low. Additionally, a modular data header structure is proposed to facilitate ISAC-aware communication, leveraging constant amplitude zero autocorrelation (CAZAC) sequences for simultaneous channel estimation and sensing.

The theoretical models address the limitations of conventional RIS channel models by incorporating mutual coupling effects and impedance mismatches. A universal framework is proposed, leveraging multiport network theory to derive equivalent models based on impedance, admittance, and scattering (S) parameters. This framework enables rigorous analysis and optimization of RIS architectures, including beyond-diagonal configurations that offer improved flexibility and performance. Numerical simulations highlight the impact of mutual coupling and RIS connectivity on received signal power, providing valuable insights for system designers. Lastly, the theoretical works look into the RIS assisted ISAC systems, including blockage modeling. Signal blockages are a major cause of losses and predicting those is an important application for ISAC. RIS is a promising technology to mitigate blockages and in general optimize the networks. It is shown that RISs can bring major benefits for ISAC system performance.

To further enhance the ISAC modeling, a ray-based ISAC modeling approach is introduced. The ray tracer employs triangle mesh-based geometry and graphics processing unit (GPU) accelerated visibility analysis to simulate complex propagation environments. This tool supports reflection, diffraction, and scattering interactions, and is capable of modeling sensing targets in INSTINCT scenarios, also with or without RISs. The ray tracer is very important when evaluating ISAC performance in dynamic and obstructed environments, where traditional models may not properly describe the surrounding environment.

2 Experimental ISAC modeling

This section looks at the experimental and practical works in INSTINCT task 1.2. First, we look into the RIS beamforming control algorithms. After that, some RIS measurements are given with consideration on RIS assisted ISAC. Lastly, we investigate security algorithms and ISAC-aware data header structures.

2.1 Mechanism of RIS beamforming control algorithm

This section aims to report on RIS measurements tackling the capabilities of the RIS to change its beamforming capabilities, namely providing a variable beam for enhanced localization and communications. The beamforming control algorithm is essentially a numerical PBP optimization in far field which intends to illuminate an area of interest. The area can be defined as per the user requirements. For instance, an area of diameter d corresponding to the beamwidth can be targeted.

The beam control PBP algorithm can be split into 2 phases: Initialization and PBP optimization.

2.1.1 Initialization phase

The initialization phase can be decomposed into the following steps:

1. Model a spherical wave incident field that takes the following form:

$$E_{in} = \frac{1}{d(r_{tx}, r_{pix})} e^{jk d(r_{tx}, r_{pix})} \cos \theta$$

where $d(r_{tx}, r_{pix}) = \sqrt{(r_{txx} - r_{pix_{ix}})^2 + (r_{txy} - r_{pix_{iy}})^2 + (r_{txz} - r_{pix_{iz}})^2} \forall i \in [1, \dots, N]$ is the Euclidian distance from the position $(r_{txx}, r_{txy}, r_{txz})$ of the transmitter (Tx) antenna to the position $(r_{pix_{ix}}, r_{pix_{iy}}, r_{pix_{iz}})$ of the i -th pixel of the RIS in cartesian coordinates. N denotes the number of pixels. $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ is the wave number, and $\cos \theta$ is the cosine prefactor, which models the incident field amplitude depending on its angle when impinging the RIS, θ .

2. Create U, V coordinates. These u, v coordinates correspond to the plane on which you are propagating the reflected planar wave in far field in spatial frequency.
3. We now need to establish the area in far field towards which we are beamforming. Here, we create a disk of diameter d which corresponds to the beamwidth length in U, V basis.
4. Create the propagation matrix spanning the basis set by U and V :

$$G_{pix_{uv}} = \cos \theta e^{jk(Ur_{pix_x} + Vr_{pix_y})}$$

where U and V are vectors of size $(1, Nu)$ and r_{pix_x} and r_{pix_y} are vectors of size $(n_{pixels}, 1)$. The resulting propagation matrix will thus be of size (n_{pixels}, Nu) .

5. Modulate the incident field with the configuration of the RIS. Once the incident field impinges on the RIS, we need to model this impingement on the MTS pixels. To obtain the reflected wave matrix, we multiply the configuration matrix of the RIS by the incident field matrix:

$$E_{reflected} = E_{in}\psi_{pix}$$

$\psi_{pix} = \{0,1\}^{n_{pixels}}$ is an array of configurations, equal to -1 in the case of 0° phase shift or equal to 1 in the case of 180° phase shift, that is of size $(n_{pixels}, 1)$, knowing that we only take the diodes for one polarization here. E_{in} is of size $(n_{pixels}, 1)$. It is thus the term-to-term multiplication of the field arriving on each pixel coordinate by the pixel configuration of the same pixel coordinate.

6. Apply the principle of Huygens to model the reflected electric field in far field:

$$E_{uv} = E_{reflected}G_{pix_{uv}}$$

7. Measure the intensity of the far-field radiation pattern:

$$I = |\phi_{uv}|^2$$

Optimize the RIS configuration according to an objective function that the network or the RIS can implement based on some input KPIs and constraints. In this work, we target at maximizing the intensity (power) of the field while minimizing its abrupt changes in the area of interest.

2.1.2 Pixel-by-pixel optimization

Now that we have initialized all necessary variables, the optimization is run numerically in far field, specifically in the targeted disk. The idea is to maximize the intensity of the radiation pattern while minimizing its changes only in the disk of interest, whose diameter corresponds to the desired beamwidth. The optimization can be demonstrated with the following pseudo-code:

ALGORITHM 1: BEAMWIDTH OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

Input: P_{goal} , E_{uv} , E_{in} , $G_{pix_{uv}}$, n_{pixels} , n_{diodes} , n_{iter}

Output: $config \in \{0, 1\}^{n_{diodes}}$, $score_list$

- 1 for i in $\{0, 1\}$ do
- 2 $best_config \leftarrow 0_{n_{pixels}}$; $current_config$ and $max_config \leftarrow best_config$
- 3 $E_{ref} \leftarrow E_{in} * (2 * best_config - 1)$
- 3 $E_{uv} \leftarrow E_{ref} @ G_{pix_{uv}}$ //where @ is the matrix product
- 4 $I \leftarrow |E_{uv}|^2$ // calculate radiation pattern from incident field modulated by config
- 5 $best_goal \leftarrow$
 Objective function: Mazimizing average power while minimizing the changes in the disk
- 6 for j in n_{iter} do
- 7 for k in $\{0, \dots, n_{pixels}\}$ do
- 8 Optimize the radiation pattern by testing the different pixels
- 21 end
- 22 end
- 23 $config \leftarrow max_config$
- 24 $states \leftarrow$ assign $config$ to $states$ for corresponding diode polarization in the order (H, V)
- 25 end

2.2 Preliminary measurements

2.2.1 Setup

2.2.1.1 Overview of setup

Figure 1: Setup diagram

The setup diagram is shown above in Figure 1. To successfully perform our measurements, the setup requires the following:

- A feedback system; a viable way to measure forward gain S_{21} . Here, it is the vector network analyser (VNA).
- A motor: It allows rotating the RIS, hence enabling the measurement of a radiation pattern. Here, it is a NEWPORT motor with its controller.
- A RIS
- 1 Tx antenna, 1 receiver (Rx) antenna with large beamwidths to illuminate well the MTS. The Tx antenna is shown to the left of Figure 1 illuminating the RIS, and the Rx antenna is shown to the right.

Figure 2: Greenerwave RIS FR2 in measurement

2.2.2 Reference Measurements

2.2.2.1 Verification of Tx/Rx Positions with PBP and Forward Model

The positions of the Tx and Rx antennas were verified and calibrated according to the forward model, which plots the radiation pattern in far field of a given configuration. To acquire this configuration, an optimization by pixel was performed in order to check the validity of the model and its corresponding radiation pattern:

Far field forward model for vertical polarization from widebeam PBP-generated config used in tests - beamwidth 3°
RIS FR2 | Central Frequency : 27 GHz

Figure 3: Left: Vertical diode of configuration from PBP optimization, passed in forward model. Right: Output of forward model; projected radiation pattern in far field.

As shown in Figure 3, the Rx antenna is almost exactly positioned at $(0^\circ, 0^\circ)$ in azimuth and elevation. It is assumed that Rx antenna respects the following constraints: $-45^\circ < az < 45^\circ$; $-45^\circ < el < 45^\circ$. If az or el lies outside of these conditions, the algorithm will most likely still beamform towards the Rx antenna, simply S_{21} received will be lower, following a cosine rule, with the maximum being aligned at the center of the RIS. The beamforming algorithm thus takes as parameters the following conversions:

$$az = \frac{180}{\pi} \arctan \frac{fx}{fz}$$

$$el = \frac{180}{\pi} \arctan \frac{fy}{fz}$$

where $x = 0$, $y = 0.74$, $z = 0.159$ are the cartesian coordinates of the Tx antenna relative to the center of the RIS. The reference is chosen according to Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: RIS Reference system when measuring Tx and Rx position parameters x, y .

2.3 RIS Measurements with beamforming control for enhanced localization and communications

2.3.1 Beam Control with Random Initialization of Illuminations Matrix as a Weight Matrix

Using the concept of pixel contributions and standard PBP optimization, one can calculate how much each pixel contributes to the gain in S_{21} by using differential illumination measurements by each pixel with respect to its neighbor. This will then give us a matrix of size $(n_{pixels_x}, n_{pixels_y})$:

Figure 5: Contribution/Illumination of Pixels for both polarizations (Note: here the polarizations are inversed due to a false diode mapping of (V, H) instead of (H, V)).

Here, we can observe the Fresnel rings for one polarization, which is expected as we are transmitting with a spherical source in a near-field. It is worth noting that this is for one position

of Rx antenna. Additionally, the pixel contributions can be characterized as either of the two following options:

1. The pixel is highly illuminated by the Tx antenna, thus reflecting a lot of power, and contributing to a higher gain when not interfering in one of the two states.
2. The pixel is very well geometrically positioned, as shown in Figure 6: Example of a geometric pixel position on the RIS in such way that the phase difference of the Rx and Tx distances from the RIS is π .

Below, RIS is positioned such that a 180° phase shift is equal to the difference of phases between the Tx distance and the Rx distance. Thus, it will contribute to an almost perfect constructive interference, whereas if another pixel on the RIS is positioned such that the difference of phases between Tx and Rx antennas is 90° , it does not matter whether the pixel shifts the impinging wave 0° or 180° because there will always be a 90° phase difference, and thus destructive interference. Thus, generating a weight matrix in which a weight is high either because the pixel is illuminated or because it is well positioned, or both, is very unreliable, and diverges from the initial goal, which is to have an idea of how well the Tx antenna illuminates the RIS. This is why one can isolate both variables and only consider the illumination of the RIS.

Figure 6: Example of a geometric pixel position on the RIS in such way that the phase difference of the Rx and Tx distances from the RIS is π .

Illumination of Pixels for all Rx positions from -60° to 60° in azimuth at 27.0 GHz

Figure 7: Illumination Weight Matrix for all Rx Positions from -60° to 60° in azimuth (Note: Correct Polarization and Diode Mapping).

We can observe in Figure 7 that the center is more illuminated than near the edges of the RIS, which confirms that pixels are not illuminated uniformly. Additionally, the horizontal diodes are barely receiving the signal which is logical since the transmission is done in a vertical polarization. This illumination matrix will thus act as a weight matrix, with 1 being the highest illumination recorded and 0 being the least amount of pixel illumination. This weight matrix will be multiplied term-to-term by the configuration in the PBP algorithm before propagating the reflected field to the far field.

The results in Figure 8 are shown below where the dotted curves are the simulated radiation patterns, and the solid curves are the measured or *ground truth* radiation patterns.

Figure 8: Simulated (dashed) and experimental (solid) S21 Curves from the same configuration generated by random widebeam PBP with kick with the illumination weight matrix applied for beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°.

First, we observe that the simulated radiation pattern is far from identical to the measured radiation pattern. Hence, a second iteration of the optimization was needed.

2.3.2 Beam control through pixel illuminations as weight matrix

2.3.2.1 Optimization Direction: 0° in azimuth, 0° in elevation

The measurements here require another approach than the proposed random one in the previous section. In this section, we propose a deterministic PBP approach. The fact that the PBP control algorithm contains random orders of which pixels were flipped, starts with a random configuration, and includes kicks that reset a certain portion of the pixels in random states, makes the results very unpredictable. Therefore, we proposed to update the optimization using the pixels as weight matrix.

The radiation patterns after the beamforming control algorithm at an optimization direction of 0° in azimuth at 27 GHz are shown in the Figures below.

Figure 9: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with Illumination Matrix applied for beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°, 11°.

Figure 10: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied for beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6° at 27 GHz- Zoom.

Figure 11: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied and beamwidths for 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°, 11° at 27 GHz.

We can observe in the figures above that the algorithm functions well for beamwidths 3° – 7°, as well as for beamwidth 9°. However, it fails to create an 8° beamwidth, falling back to around 6.5°, and also creates dips for beamwidths 10° and 11°. One of the possible reasons is that the rectified beamwidths passed to the second widebeam PBP are off.

At 28 GHz, as shown in

Figure 12: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied and beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9° at 28 GHz.

Figure 12: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied and beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9° at 28 GHz.

2.3.2.2 Optimization in other directions

In order to validate the algorithm, it needs to be tested at multiple optimization directions and needs to be stable and consistent. We thus tested here the deterministic PBP rectified beamwidths using the illuminations weight matrix. The results are shown below.

Figure 13: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied for beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7° at 27 GHz in all designated optimization directions.

We observe similar behavior in the widebeamforming algorithm at 28 GHz compared to 27 GHz. Many measured beamwidths were at 4° – 4.5° , and the 7° beamwidth generated a 3.5° beamwidth and a 6° beamwidth.

In Figure 14, the beamwidths are still off, reaching a maximum error of 2° and a mean error of 1.25° . The measured beamwidth for an expected beamwidth 10° is 8° . In Figure 15, a 9.5° beamwidth is achieved at an optimization direction of 40° . The mean error for beamwidths 3° – 7° is of 0.75 . Overall, the proposed control algorithm works quite well with some errors in given directions. This should be studied in the future to fine tune the proposed algorithm.

Figure 14: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied for beamwidths 3° , 4° , 5° , 6° , 7° , 10° at 27 GHz at optimization direction 20° .

Figure 15: S21 Curve from deterministic Widebeam PBP with illumination Matrix applied for beamwidths 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 10° at 27 GHz at optimization direction 40°.

2.4 Integration of RIS in physical layer security setup

The communication channel between the legitimate users is reciprocal in nature while due to the spatial decorrelation, the channel observed at the eavesdropper will be non-reciprocal as represented in Figure 16. Here, Alice and Bob are legitimate users under an eavesdropping attack from Eve [1]. In physical layer security, these properties are used to extract secret keys from the measured signals at the legitimate users in the physical layer security [2][3]. The key generation rate depends on the randomness of the channel. For the dynamic channels, the channel coherence time is shorter than the static channels where it tends to infinity. Hence, there is very less randomness observed in the channel which makes the keys generated in such channels vulnerable and susceptible to attacks [4].

Figure 16: System model for secret key generation between legitimate users under eavesdropping attack. Here, we can denote this as, $r_A(t) \approx r_B(t) \neq r_E(t)$ [5].

2.4.1 USRP-Based channel measurements:

The current demonstrator hardware configuration comprises Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) X410 devices, operating at a carrier frequency of 3.75 GHz with a sampling rate of 491.52 megasamples per second (MS/s). This setup yields a usable bandwidth of approximately 400 MHz, enabling high-throughput signal processing capabilities. To ensure coherent operation, the two USRPs are synchronized via a shared reference clock and a common time source, thereby facilitating time-aligned transmission and reception of frames. A photograph of the existing hardware arrangement is provided in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Demonstrator hardware setup featuring two synchronized USRP X410 devices.

Notably, the system architecture is inherently scalable, allowing for straightforward expansion to support multiple USRP devices as required by future use cases.

The structure of the measurements and the transmitted signals is depicted in Figure X. In this experimental setup, two nodes—designated Alice and Bob—exchange frames in a burst-mode configuration. Each measurement cycle involves the exchange of **NUM_FRAMES = 5** frames; however, for illustration purposes, only three frames are shown in the figure. A temporal interval of **FRAME_DELAY = 0.1 s** is introduced between successive frames to mitigate inter-frame

interference and to simulate realistic communication scenarios. Additionally, a fixed transmission delay of **DELAY_AB = 0.01 s** is imposed between Alice and Bob to emulate channel propagation characteristics.

Each frame comprises a chirp signal of 2048 samples, occupying the full available bandwidth of 400 MHz. After frame exchange, the secret keys can be extracted by the secret key generation algorithm. Figure 18 shows the reciprocal channel between Alice and Bob and the decorrelated channel observed by Eve for the Eve–Alice and Eve–Bob channels.

Figure 18: Frequency domain channels observed by Alice, Bob and Eve

Measurements Done in Different Environments

The measurements and real-time carrier frequency references (CFRs) were captured across the following three distinct scenarios:

- **Line-of-sight, static positions (LOS-Static):** Both USRPs remained stationary with a direct line-of-sight (LOS) path between them.
- **Non-line-of-sight, static positions (NLOS-Static):** Both USRPs remained stationary without a direct LOS path between them.
- **Dynamic USRPs (Dynamic):** Both USRPs were in motion during the measurement.

Based on the measurements in the different scenarios, the obtained secret key rates are shown in the Figure 19 below.

Figure 19: Secret key generation rate in bits per frame exchanged between Alice and Bob in the presence of Eve under different environments.

2.4.2 Secret key generation aided by RIS based channels

As seen, the static channel has very less key rates compared to dynamic channels due to less randomness present in the channel. In order to overcome this, we use RIS to help in increasing the SKG rates. This can be achieved by increasing the randomness and entropy in the channel by altering the multipath propagation. RIS aids in increasing the channel reciprocity by beamforming to increase the SNR towards the legitimate users.

In the proposed system, RIS phase configurations are updated periodically during the frame exchange process. These updates are synchronized with the measurement and transmission schedule, ensuring that both Alice and Bob observe the same randomized channel instances for each measurement window.

The resulting channel can be modelled as,

$$h_{eff}(t) = h_d(t) + h_r^{(H)}(t) * \theta(t) * h_t(t),$$

where $h_{eff}(t) \in \mathbb{C}$ is the effective channel coefficient at time t , for both direct path and path reflected by RIS, $h_d(t) \in \mathbb{C}$ is the direct channel between Alice and Bob, $h_t(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the channel vector from Alice to RIS with N elements, $h_r(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the channel vector from RIS to Bob with N elements, $\theta(t) = \text{diag}(e^{j\theta_1 t}, e^{j\theta_2 t}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N t})$ is the diagonal matrix of RIS phase shifts, $(\cdot)^H$ is the complex conjugate transpose.

Since the channel is reciprocal, for the same configuration of RIS,

$$h_{eff}(t)^{Alice \rightarrow Bob} \approx h_{eff}(t)^{Bob \rightarrow Alice}.$$

In the further works, we will integrate a RIS in the USRP based setup and evaluate the SKG rates for different scenarios.

2.5 ISAC-aware data header structure

2.5.1 Integration of channel state information (CSI) estimation and sensing procedure

Rather than relying on theoretical or experimental channel models for predicting the behavior of a ISAC setup, this section looks into a way to approach the topic from a reactive, model-agnostic, estimation-based angle. In traditional communication experiments, a data-aided transmission with a three-stage header sequence for solving various problems *a posteriori* via digital signal processing (DSP) has been the preferred solution. This necessitates the compartmentalization of continuous point-to-point (P2P) data streams into frames, with a fixed portion of each dedicated to the header known by both communication parties, and the rest constituted by the payload data.

2.5.2 Header structure

The modular header sequence available in HHI's toolbox consists of separate sequence blocks dedicated to specific tasks. While each part can be individually toggled on or off and the sequence type for each block can be chosen from a number of options, the most robust configuration is structured as follows:

1. A PRBS-5 sequence with a fixed initial state for detecting and synchronizing the beginning of a frame.
2. A custom 8-symbol BPSK sequence, repeated 8 times, with a guard interval for suppressing unwanted aliasing components, for estimating the frequency offset between Tx and Rx carrier frequency. While frequency offset estimation (FOE) can remove most of the misalignment between the carriers on the basis of this short sequence block, a residual error in the range of a few MHz usually remains. More complex functions can compensate for this down the Rx DSP chain.

3. Lastly, a 64-symbol Constant Amplitude Zero AutoCorrelation (CAZAC) sequence is repeated 4 times and padded by a guard interval. This serves as the training sequence for a data-aided, frequency domain equalizer, which estimates the frequency response of the channel and then equalizes the received payload signal.

Figure 20: Constellation diagram of header symbols and overhead for standard frame size.

For typical fiberoptic as well as wireless THz P2P communication channels, setting the frame size between 16,384 and 32,768 symbols is common. With the header structure and size as described above – additionally depicted in Figure 20 – the data-aided transmission can be facilitated with an overhead of 1.5-3 %, not including forward error correction (FEC), which is not required with advanced DSP.

2.5.3 Adaptation to ISAC scenarios

This implementation lends itself to exploration within an ISAC context, because CAZAC waveforms are of interest to Radar communications due to their specific characteristics. Their constant amplitude results in an ideal peak-to-average-power ratio (PAPR), thereby benefitting the performance of amplifiers in the signal chain. As a subset poly-phase sequences, they possess certain chirp-like qualities, enabling us to use them to integrate sensing into an existing communication system. Moreover, the DSP setup is optimized for single-carrier wideband modulation with a high symbol rate, which compresses the signal pulses and results in a fine sensing resolution at range.

Integrating the sensing waveform into the header sequence of the data frame is desirable, as it minimizes technical complexity and preserves communication throughput. Instead of pausing the communication to perform sensing and then resuming, both tasks happen virtually in parallel and with shared hard- and software. Two tradeoffs can be identified here which require commitment to optimizing one functionality over the other:

- Firstly, the length or number of repetitions of the employed CAZAC sequence relates to its total energy. For good detection of a radar target, enough energy must be transmitted to receive a significant signature. This is especially crucial in monostatic configurations, i.e. ISAC Tx and Rx terminal are co-located, because the received signal always travels twice the distance from the ISAC transceiver to the target. On the other hand, keeping the number of symbols dedicated to the training sequence as small as possible is essential for limiting the overhead. As detailed in the description of the header structure, the CAZAC sequence is by far the longest of the three. In the pure communication setup, the length of one individual sequence translates directly into the frequency resolution of the data-aided equalizer and the number of repetitions serves to average out noise and improve stability. When fusing communication and sensing, an additional requirement is placed on these parameters, which will have to be optimized jointly with the rest of the system's characteristics.
- Secondly, when CAZAC sequences in the frame header are used for sensing, the frame rate is equal to the sensing rate. Assuming a single-carrier wideband scenario with a symbol rate of 2 GB and frame lengths as detailed above, sensing rates in the range of tens of MHz could be achieved. It is debatable whether this is useful – updating the radar cross section (RCS) only makes sense if the distance travelled by a moving object exceeds the range resolution of the sensing system. The absolute KPI is therefore dependent on the maximum expected velocity of the objects in the detection space and the resolution – either at range or in the angular domain, albeit under constraints for the detection range – which are in turn governed by the carrier frequency and bandwidth of the ISAC node. It might not be necessary to use every frame header for sensing and some CAZAC sequences could be made longer to increase their total energy and thus improve target detection while the overhead remains constant on average.

2.5.4 Summary of the data header

We propose utilizing our existing data-aided framework for high symbol rates, single-carrier communication experience and adapting the header structure to suit the requirements of ISAC scenarios. Training sequences in the frame header are already used to estimate the communication channel and expanding the utilization of CAZAC sequences could provide additional sensing information. This approach represents a model-agnostic, reactive, and reconfigurable method of obtaining knowledge about the environment with a ISAC system.

3 Theoretical ISAC Modeling

In this section, we look at the more theoretical works performed in INSTINCT task 1.2. Firstly, we look at RIS modeling via network theory. Then we derive a mutual coupling aware RIS channel model and look at signal blockage models. Finally, this section looks into RIS assisted ISAC systems.

3.1 Multiport Network Theory for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

RIS is a promising technology expected to revolutionize future wireless systems [9]. An RIS is a surface made of multiple scattering elements, each of which can be reconfigured to impose an adaptive phase shift to the incident electromagnetic (EM) waves. In this way, an RIS can dynamically manipulate the EM properties of the propagation environment, and enable the so-called concept of smart radio environment [10]. Since an RIS can manipulate the incident signal in a nearly passive manner, it is also a cost-effective solution characterized by low power consumption.

A substantial number of studies on RIS have been devoted to system optimization. Specifically, RIS has been optimized to enhance the performance of wireless communication systems, including single-cell [11], [12], multi-cell [13], multi-RIS [14], and wideband communications [15]. Meanwhile, RIS has been integrated with multiple access schemes such as nonorthogonal multiple access (NOMA) [16] and rate splitting multiple access (RSMA) [17], to ease the requirement of complex signal processing at the transmitter. In addition to wireless communication systems, RIS has been also applied to wireless power transfer (WPT) systems [18], simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) systems [19], radio frequency (RF) sensing systems [20], and dual-function radar-communication (DFRC) systems [21]. While the aforementioned works [11]–[21] apply an idealized RIS model, research has been conducted to optimize RIS in the presence of discretized reflection coefficients through low-complexity codebook designs [22], [23], imperfect channel state information (CSI) [24], and mutual coupling [25]–[31]. Furthermore, RIS has been prototyped in [32], [33], and [34], demonstrating its practicability.

The authors of [11]–[34] have considered the optimization of conventional RIS architectures. In a conventional RIS architecture, also known as single-connected RIS, the reflection coefficient of each RIS element is individually controlled through a tunable load, resulting in a diagonal scattering matrix [35]. Recently, a novel advance in RIS, namely beyond diagonal RIS (BD-RIS), has been proposed [36], which relies on novel RIS architectures yielding scattering matrices not limited to being diagonal. The conventional RIS architecture has been first generalized by interconnecting groups of/all the RIS elements to each other through tunable impedance components, resulting in the group-/fully-connected architectures, respectively [35]. Group and

fully-connected RIS have been optimized assuming continuous-valued impedances [37], [38], considering discrete valued impedances [39], and in the presence of mutual coupling [40]. Forest-connected and tree-connected RIS have been proposed in [41] to achieve the same performance enhancement as group- and fully-connected RIS, respectively, but at a reduced circuit complexity. Furthermore, the RIS architectures achieving the best trade-off between performance and circuit complexity have been characterized in [42]. BD-RIS architectures have been investigated also with the objective of achieving full-space coverage, by reflecting and transmitting the incident signal [43]. To improve the performance while preserving full-space coverage, multisector BD-RIS has been proposed [44] - [46]. Different from the fixed BD-RIS architectures studied in [35] - [46], dynamic BD-RIS architectures have been studied in [47] and [48], where higher flexibility is achieved by reconfiguring the interconnections among the RIS elements on a per channel realization basis. An additional RIS architecture with a non-diagonal response is the so-called stacked intelligent metasurface (SIM), recently proposed to offer additional flexibility by staking multiple single-connected RISs [49], whose communication model has been analyzed in [51].

While most of the research on conventional RIS and BD-RIS has primarily focused on RIS optimization [11] - [34] and on RIS architecture development [35] - [50], only a few works have been devoted to model and analyze RIS-aided communication systems accounting for the EM properties of the RIS, such as impedance mismatching and mutual coupling [51]. With a focus on RIS modeled as an antenna array connected to a reconfigurable impedance network, three equivalent analyses are available to show the role of RIS in wireless networks from different perspectives. First, in [35], an RIS-aided communication model has been derived using multiport network analysis based on scattering parameters. Second, in [52], another RIS-aided communication model has been developed by using the impedance parameters. Interestingly, it has been shown in [53] that the scattering parameters analysis of [35] and the impedance parameters analysis of [52] lead to the same conclusion under the assumptions of perfect matching and no mutual coupling. Third, another analysis based on admittance parameters has been proposed in [41] to model BD-RIS with sparse interconnections among the RIS elements. However, there is currently no universal framework for modeling RIS-aided systems according to impedance, admittance, and scattering parameters, as well as clarifying the meaning of the different components in each model, despite their equivalence being well-established in microwave theory. Such a framework would improve our understanding of different EM-consistent models for RIS-aided systems, and would provide additional tools to perform RIS optimization. Furthermore, it would enable a thorough analysis of the impact of each approximation and assumption necessary to simplify existing RIS-aided communication models based on the different parameters.

Motivated by the above considerations, in this paper, we move from existing works on EM-consistent RIS-aided communication models [35], [52], [53] and derive a universal framework to analyze RIS-aided communication systems. This universal framework can be used to carry out a rigorous multiport network analysis of RIS-aided communication systems based on impedance, admittance, and scattering parameters, also denoted as Z -, Y -, and S parameters, respectively. As a result of these analyses, we can derive three RIS-aided communication models accounting

for mutual coupling effects and impedance mismatching at the transmitter, RIS, and receiver. Our universal framework shows the equivalence between channel models based on Z -, Y -, and S -parameters also under different assumptions and approximations. This is achieved by providing the mappings between the terms of the models based on the three different parameters. Moreover, we show that, under specific assumptions, the derived channel models boil down to models already used in previous literature, confirming the soundness and rigorousness of our analysis.

In this work, we propose a universal framework to derive EM-consistent communication models for RIS-aided systems. We exploit the proposed universal framework to analyze RIS-aided communication systems based on the Z -, Y -, and S -parameters. Through these three independent analyses, we first derive three general channel models, accounting for the effects of impedance mismatching and mutual coupling at the transmitter, RIS, and receiver, which can significantly impact the performance of practical RIS designs. Then, we show for the first time that the three derived models are equivalent when no approximations or assumptions are made.

3.1.1 Proposed model

We consider a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communication system aided by an RIS, where there are N_T antennas at the transmitter, N_R antennas at the receiver, and N_I scattering elements at the RIS, as represented in the following figure:

Figure 21: Considered multiport network model

As in [35], we model the wireless channel as an N-port network, with $N = N_T + N_I + N_R$. According to multiport network analysis [55, Chapter 4], this N-port network can be characterized by using its impedance, admittance, or scattering matrix. The following table reports the configuration of the model for different implementations of RIS:

Table 1: Multiport network models for different RIS types

	Z-parameters	Y-parameters	S-parameters
Single-connected	$\mathbf{Z}_I = \text{diag}(Z_1, \dots, Z_{N_I})$, $Z_{n_I} = jX_{n_I}, X_{n_I} \in \mathbb{R}, \forall n_I$	$\mathbf{Y}_I = \text{diag}(Y_1, \dots, Y_{N_I})$, $Y_{n_I} = jB_{n_I}, B_{n_I} \in \mathbb{R}, \forall n_I$	$\Theta = \text{diag}(\Theta_1, \dots, \Theta_{N_I})$, $\Theta_{n_I} = e^{j\theta_{n_I}}, \theta_{n_I} \in [0, 2\pi), \forall n_I$
Fully-connected	$\mathbf{Z}_I = j\mathbf{X}_I, \mathbf{X}_I = \mathbf{X}_I^T, \mathbf{X}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{N_I \times N_I}$	$\mathbf{Y}_I = j\mathbf{B}_I, \mathbf{B}_I = \mathbf{B}_I^T, \mathbf{B}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{N_I \times N_I}$	$\Theta^H \Theta = \mathbf{I}, \Theta = \Theta^T$
Group-connected	$\mathbf{Z}_I = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Z}_{I,1}, \dots, \mathbf{Z}_{I,G})$, $\mathbf{Z}_{I,g} = j\mathbf{X}_{I,g}, \mathbf{X}_{I,g} = \mathbf{X}_{I,g}^T, \mathbf{X}_{I,g} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{I,g} \times N_{I,g}}, \forall g$	$\mathbf{Y}_I = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Y}_{I,1}, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_{I,G})$, $\mathbf{Y}_{I,g} = j\mathbf{B}_{I,g}, \mathbf{B}_{I,g} = \mathbf{B}_{I,g}^T, \mathbf{B}_{I,g} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{I,g} \times N_{I,g}}, \forall g$	$\Theta = \text{diag}(\Theta_1, \dots, \Theta_G)$, $\Theta_g^H \Theta_g = \mathbf{I}, \Theta_g = \Theta_g^T, \forall g$
Tree-connected*	–	$\mathbf{Y}_I = j\mathbf{B}_I, \mathbf{B}_I = \mathbf{B}_I^T, \mathbf{B}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{N_I \times N_I}$, $[\mathbf{B}_I]_{i,j} = 0 \text{ if } i - j > 1$	–
Forest-connected*	–	$\mathbf{Y}_I = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Y}_{I,1}, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_{I,G})$, $\mathbf{Y}_{I,g} = j\mathbf{B}_{I,g}, \mathbf{B}_{I,g} = \mathbf{B}_{I,g}^T, \mathbf{B}_{I,g} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{I,g} \times N_{I,g}}$, $[\mathbf{B}_{I,g}]_{i,j} = 0 \text{ if } i - j > 1, \forall g$	–
Application	Optimization w/ mutual coupling	Optimization of BD-RIS with sparse \mathbf{Y}_I	Optimization w/o mutual coupling

3.1.2 Numerical results

In this section, we evaluate the performance obtained by solving the three optimization problems presented herein, using the Z-, Y-, and S-parameters. The transmitter, RIS, and receiver are located at (0, 0), (50, 2), and (52, 0) meters (m), respectively. We set $N_T = 2$ and $N_R = 2$, and assume that the direct channel between the transmitter and receiver is completely obstructed, i.e., $Z_{RT} = 0$. For the large-scale path loss of the channels from the RIS to the receiver and from the transmitter to the RIS, we use the distance-dependent path loss model $L_{ij}(d_{ij}) = L_{0d} - \alpha_{ij}$, where L_0 is the reference path loss at distance 1 m, d_{ij} is the distance, and α_{ij} is the path loss exponent, for $ij \in \{RI, IT\}$. We set $L_0 = -30$ dB, $\alpha_{RI} = 2.8$, $\alpha_{IT} = 2$, and $P_T = 10$ mW. For the smallscale fading, we model the channels as i.i.d. Rayleigh, i.e., $S_{RI} \sim \text{CN}(0, L_{RI})$ and $S_{IT} \sim \text{CN}(0, L_{IT})$. Given Z_{RT} , S_{RI} , and S_{IT} , we obtain the rest of the off-diagonal blocks of Z, Y, and S.

In the Figure 22 we report the average received signal power obtained by optimizing the RIS through the Z-, Y-, and S-parameters:

Figure 22: Average received signal power as a function of number of RIS elements.

In the case of group- and forest-connected RISs, the group size is $N_G = 4$. The schemes “w/o Mutual Coupling” are obtained by setting $Z_{II} = Z_{0I}$. Besides, the schemes “w/ Mutual Coupling” in figure(a) are obtained by modeling Z_{II} as follows: its diagonal entries are set to Z_0 , assuming perfectly matched RIS elements, while its off-diagonal entries are modeled as in [33], considering the RIS antennas being dipoles with length $\ell = \lambda/4$ and inter-element distance $d = \lambda/4$, where $\lambda = c/f$ is the wavelength with frequency $f = 28$ GHz. We make the following observations.

First, BD-RIS outperforms single-connected RIS in the presence of mutual coupling because of its higher flexibility, in agreement with [39], and also in the absence of mutual coupling since Rayleigh fading is considered [35], [41].

Second, the presence of mutual coupling between the RIS elements increases the performance, in accordance with [29]. We observe this gain for all the considered RIS architectures by assuming that the RIS mutual coupling matrix Z_{II} is perfectly known during the optimization process.

Third, in the absence of mutual coupling, single-/group-/fully-connected RIS architectures optimized based on the Z-parameters achieve the same performance as the same architectures optimized based on the S-parameters, providing additional evidence of the equivalence of the two analyses. In the considered case study, optimizing based on the S-parameters is preferred since closed-form solutions are available, leading to a low-complexity optimization process [36].

Fourth, in the absence of mutual coupling, single-/group-/fully-connected RISs optimized by using the S-parameters achieve the same performance as single-/forest-/tree-connected RISs optimized with the Y-parameters, respectively, in agreement with [41]. In the considered case study, forest-/tree-connected RISs are preferred over group-/fully-connected RISs, since they are characterized by a reduced circuit complexity [41].

3.2 Mutual coupling aware channel model with RIS

As the design of RISs moves beyond traditional flat architectures with half-wavelength ($\lambda/2$) spacing between elements, it increasingly embraces larger, more complex surfaces. For example: holographic surfaces, which are characterized by a much denser arrangement of elements, with sub- $\lambda/2$ spacing, and the so-called conformal surfaces, where elements are arranged on non-planar deployment environments. These RIS design settings introduce structural complexities that give rise to intricate EM phenomena, such as strong mutual coupling among closely packed elements, spatially varying surface impedance, and the emergence of nontrivial re-radiation fields [6], [7]. These effects are not captured by conventional simplified models and, if neglected, can lead to unintended scattering, degraded beamforming, and overall reduced system performance [6], [8]. Accurate modeling is thus required to predict and control the behavior of these complex surfaces, ensure efficient transmission and reception, and fully exploit the wave manipulation capabilities that next-generation RIS designs aim to offer.

In this contribution [6], we provide a mutual coupling aware model suitable for conformal and holographic RIS. Specifically, in the case of single antenna transmitter (T), single antenna receiver (R) and N elements RIS (S) the end-to-end channel is given by

$$H = Y_0 [Z_{RT} - \mathbf{z}_{SR}^T (\mathbf{Z}_{SS} + \mathbf{Z}_{RIS})^{-1} \mathbf{z}_{ST}]$$

where the subscripts R, T, and S stand for the UE, the BS, and the RIS, respectively. $Y^0 = Z_L (Z_L + Z_{RR})^{-1} (Z_G + Z_{TT})^{-1} \in \mathbb{C}$ is a fixed constant, and Z_L and Z_G are the load impedances of the UE and the BS antennas. Z_{RR} and Z_{TT} denote the self-impedances at the UE and BS. Z_{RT} represents the direct channel between the BS and the UE, $\mathbf{z}_{SR} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the impedance between each of the RIS elements and the antenna of the UR, which represents the channel between the RIS and the UE, and $\mathbf{z}_{ST} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the impedance between the RIS elements and the transmitter antenna, representing the channel between the BS and the RIS. $\mathbf{Z}_{SS} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the matrix of self and mutual impedances among RIS elements, and $\mathbf{Z}_{RIS} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the matrix of tunable RIS impedances, which accounts for the RIS configuration.

The received signal at the receiver is thus given by $y = Hx + n$, where x is the transmitted symbol, and n is the receiver noise. The RIS tunable impedance matrix can be modeled as

$$Z_{RIS} = \text{diag}\{R_0 + j b_k\} \text{ for } k = 1 \text{ to } N$$

where $R_0 \geq 0$ accounts for losses in internal circuits, and b_k is the tunable reactance at the k -th element. Entries of \mathbf{Z}_{SS} , and the values of Z_{RT} , \mathbf{z}_{SR} , and \mathbf{z}_{ST} can be obtained numerically with method of moments-based analysis, or full wave simulator tools for example CST. The same applies to \mathbf{z}_{SR} , \mathbf{z}_{ST} , and Z_{RT} . In the case of simple antenna structures, for example the thin wire dipoles of length $\lambda/2$. Mutual impedance values can be computed analytically [6]. For example, in the case of two thin dipoles at positions \mathbf{q}_q and \mathbf{q}_p and oriented towards the z axis, i.e., parallel to $\mathbf{e}_3 = [0,0,1]^T$, the mutual impedance can be computed as

$$Z_{qp} = \frac{\eta}{8\pi} \sum_{s_o=\{1,-1\}} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} s_o \mathbf{e}_3^T \delta_{qp}} [T_0(\delta_{qp} - 2h\mathbf{e}_3, s_o) + T_0(\delta_{qp} + 2h\mathbf{e}_3, s_o) - 2T_0(\delta_{qp}, s_o)]$$

where $\eta = 377 \Omega$ is the free-space impedance, h is the dipole half-length, and $\delta_{qp} = \mathbf{q}_q - \mathbf{q}_p$, and $T_0(\boldsymbol{\zeta}, s_0) = E_1(jk(\|\boldsymbol{\zeta}\| + s_0 \mathbf{e}_3^T \boldsymbol{\zeta}))$. Here, $s_0 \in \{-1, 1\}$, and $E_1(z)$ is the exponential integral: $E_1(z) = \int_z^\infty \frac{e^{-t}}{t} dt$.

The proposed model is capable of capturing the mutual coupling effect intrinsic of advanced RIS design including non-planar and holographic surfaces.

3.3 Blockage profiling in RIS-assisted systems

In the low GHz spectral range, waves are able to bend around obstacles, because the wavelength lies within the same order of magnitude with the size of small everyday objects. With increasing frequency, however, this bending capability gradually fades, giving place to ray-like propagation, where beams evolve practically along straight paths. In view of the possible utilization of a large spectral range, spanning from sub-6 GHz (FR1) up to above 24 GHz (FR2), in this section we assess the impact of blockage across a wide frequency spectrum by means of numerical simulations.

3.3.1 Theoretical framework for beam propagation simulations

To study the impact of blockage on beams generated by planar apertures, such as uniform planar arrays (UPAs) or RISs, consider a beam propagating along the z -axis, with its footprint extending on the xy -plane. The vector of the beam's electric field at position $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$ is $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$. The E -field of the beam at distance z can be expressed in the k -space domain, using the beam's two-dimensional Fourier transform [54], as

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}(k_x, k_y; z) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathbf{E}(x, y, z) e^{-j(k_x x + k_y y)} dx dy,$$

where x, y are the Cartesian transverse coordinates and k_x, k_y the corresponding spatial frequencies; the hat denotes operation in k -space. Similarly, the inverse Fourier transform reads

$$\mathbf{E}(x, y, z) = \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{\mathbf{E}}(k_x, k_y; z) e^{j(k_x x + k_y y)} dk_x dk_y$$

Note that the field \mathbf{E} and its Fourier transform $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ represent vectors and, hence, the Fourier integrals hold separately for each vector component. The field has to satisfy Maxwell's equations, which for free-space propagation reduce to the vector Helmholtz equation $(\nabla^2 + k^2)\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{0}$; ∇^2 is the Laplacian operator, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wavenumber and λ is the wavelength. An identical equation holds for the \mathbf{H} -field. If the beam propagates for a small distance δz , we may express its field at $z + \delta z$, $\mathbf{E}(x, y; z + \delta z)$, via its Fourier transform. Inserting it into the Helmholtz equation, we find that the Fourier spectrum of the beam at distance δz is expressed in terms of its Fourier spectrum at z , as

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}(k_x, k_y; z + \delta z) = \hat{\mathbf{E}}(k_x, k_y; z) e^{jk_z \delta z}$$

where $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$. Hence, we may write the beam propagation from z to $z + \delta z$ as

$$\mathbf{E}(x, y, z + \delta z) = \mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}^{-1}\{\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}[\mathbf{E}(x, y, z)]e^{jk_z\delta z}\}$$

where $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}$ denotes the two-dimensional Fourier transform and $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}^{-1}$ its inverse [55]. To propagate a beam from the UPA/RIS, we can divide the entire distance into small steps and apply above equation repeatedly, using the output beam of the previous step as input to the next step.

Figure 23: Blockage of a narrow beam (5 deg. beamwidth) at 5 GHz (top row panels) and 30 GHz (bottom row panels). (a) Horizontal beam cross-section. (b) Power along the beam center in the absence (green) and presence (black) of a square blocker of size 0.2 m × 0.2 m, located at z = 15 m. (c) On-axis power ratio, i.e. ratio of the curves shown in panel (b).

Numerical simulations of beam propagation using the above scheme [56] are demonstrated in Figure 23. The beam is generated by a Tx equipped with a radiating aperture (e.g. UPA, RIS) of rectangular shape and evolves along the z-axis, where a Rx is located. The Tx is located at the origin of the coordinate system and the Rx can be located anywhere along the z-axis. In the top row panels, the operation frequency is 5 GHz, and the Tx aperture has dimensions 0.61 m × 0.61 m, generating a beam with full width half maximum (FWHM) extent of 5 degrees. In the bottom row panels the operation frequency is 30 GHz and, to generate a beam with the same beamwidth of 5 deg., the Tx aperture has dimensions 0.1 m × 0.1 m. In both scenarios, an opaque square of side 0.2 m is located at z = 15 m (with its surface extending on the xy-plane), partially blocking the beam and causing an abrupt power drop right after, as shown in Figure 23 (a).

Because the Rx is located along the beam center, it is instructive to calculate the beam power along the z-axis (beam center), i.e., the on-axis power. The on-axis power for both scenarios is shown in Figure 23 (b). Evidently, with increasing frequency, diffraction becomes weaker, resulting in a larger shadow behind the square blocker and, consequently, a stronger power drop. To compare the two cases, in Figure 23 (c) the ratio of the on-axis beam power with and without the blocker is calculated using the respective results from Figure 23 (b).

3.3.2 Study of blockage

The study of blockage involves several parameters, including the operation frequency, the beamwidth, the size of the blocker and the location of the blocker with respect to the Tx and the

Rx. To understand the impact of blockage on the power received by an Rx, in what follows we present several propagation scenarios in which we study the impact of the above parameters individually.

Figure 24: On-axis power ratio, as a function of the operation frequency. The blocker is an opaque square located 10 m in front of the Tx. Blockage becomes stronger with narrower beams and larger blockers.

3.3.3 Impact of operation frequency on blockage

First, we examine the shadow behind the blocker as a function of the operation frequency. To this end, we use a narrow beam of 5 degrees. FWHM to calculate the on-axis power ratio for an extended spectral ranging 5 GHz – 30 GHz, see Figure 24, top row panels. The blocker is located at $z = 10$ m and, to have a fair comparison, as we increase the frequency we decrease the Tx's aperture size accordingly, so that all generated beams have the same beamwidth of 5 degrees. Clearly, with increasing frequency the shadow extent behind the blocker increases, as expected. At low frequencies the beam is able to partially restore, however with increasing frequency this ability is gradually lost. This effect becomes more dramatic when the blocker size increases. Here, for an opaque square of side 1 m, the narrow beam is almost entirely blocked.

In Figure 24, bottom row panels, the simulations are repeated for wider beams of 30 deg. FWHM. Again, the beamwidth is constant across the entire spectral range, by adjusting the Tx's aperture size. Again, with increasing frequency, the blocker's shadow increases, yet the on-axis power ratio is higher with respect to that of narrower beams. This is particularly apparent at low frequencies, where beam diffraction is stronger; due to the wider beamwidth, the beam is able to better restore the power drop behind the blocker. This is also evident even with a large blocker of 1 side.

In the power ratio maps of Figure 24 no information about the Rx's location is provided, which could be located anywhere along the z-axis. In these results, the horizontal axis can be translated

as the possible Rx location. Clearly, the Rx receives the maximum 100% of the intended power, if located anywhere between the Tx and the blocker. For an Rx located after the blocker, the received power depends on the exact Tx-blocker-Rx topology.

3.3.4 Impact of Tx-blocker-Rx topology on blockage

In the previous examples the blocker was static at $z = 10$ m and the Rx could be located anywhere along the z -axis. Next, to study the impact of the Tx-blocker-Rx topology on blockage, we introduce longitudinal and lateral displacements to the blocker's position. In the following examples we choose $f = 5$ GHz as the operation frequency.

In Figure 25 we calculate the on-axis power ratio for $f = 5$ GHz and variable blocker's distance from the Tx. Essentially, the horizontal and vertical axis of the color plots denote the Rx's location and blocker's displacement along the z -axis, which are denoted as Z_{Rx} and $Z_{blocker}$, respectively. For a narrow beam and a $0.5 \text{ m} \times 0.5 \text{ m}$ blocker close to the Tx the power at the Rx is suppressed, regardless of the exact location of the Rx; see, for example the results for $Z_{blocker} = 5$ m. A similar conclusion is also drawn when the blocker is close to the Rx; see, for example, the results slightly to the right of the diagonal $Z_{blocker} = Z_{Rx}$. Hence, the power at the Rx is most suppressed when the blocker is either very close to the Tx or very close to the Rx. In the former case, the blocker practically blocks the beam at its very beginning; in the latter case, the blocker creates a shadow right in front of the Rx. For intermediate locations, the beam power can be restored to some extent, which depends on the blocker's size, as well as the beamwidth. This is illustrated in the remaining three panels of Figure 25.

In Figure 26 we introduce to the blocker a lateral, i.e., along the x -axis, displacement. Essentially, the horizontal and vertical axis of the color plots denote the Rx's location along the z -axis and the blocker's displacement along the x -axis, which are denoted as Z_{Rx} and $X_{blocker}$, respectively. It is no surprise that for large $|X_{blocker}|$, where the blocker hardly interacts with the beam, the power at the Rx reaches the maximum 100%, regardless of the beamwidth and the blocker's size. What is interesting is that there are blocker's displacements for which the power locally exceeds the maximum 100%. This fact does not imply power levels higher than what can be transmitted; the total beam power remains constant, as also verified by numerically integrating the beam across the xy -plane for all propagation distances. It is a local property, which is due to diffraction effects that lead to constructive interference behind the blocker. Interestingly, contrary to what might be intuitively expected, the on-axis power ratio is not the lowest when $X_{blocker} = 0$, rather when the blocker is slightly shifted from the z -axis. This observation is also due to diffraction effects that lead to constructive interference behind the blocker.

Figure 25: On-axis power ratio, as a function of the blocker's distance from the Tx (operation frequency $f = 5$ GHz). The blocker is an opaque square located in front of the Tx, at variable distance (see vertical axis in color plots). Blockage becomes stronger when the blocker is very close to the Tx or the Rx.

Figure 26: On-axis power ratio, as a function of the blocker's displacement from the Tx's broadside (operation frequency $f = 5$ GHz). The blocker is an opaque square located 10 m in front of the Tx, with variable displacement along the transverse direction (see vertical axis in color plots).

3.4 RIS-assisted Millimeter-wave Integrated Sensing and Communication Systems

In recent years, due to the similarity between radar and communication in terms of hardware components and signal processing algorithms, as well as the scarcity of spectrum resources, ISAC has emerged as one of the key technologies for 6G [57]-[59]. The sensing function collects and extracts useful information from noisy observations, and the communication function is intended to transmit information through specialized signals and recover the transmitted information from noisy received signals. In terms of hardware, ISAC is intended to integrate these two functions aiming for a tradeoff between them, which is expected to significantly improve the spectral and energy efficiencies and to reduce the cost of the hardware as well. In terms of applications, ISAC can provide users with high-quality communication performance while providing high-precision sensing performance in terms of target detection. In general, ISAC has broad application prospects in areas, such as smart home, smart transportation, and smart medical care [60].

However, the integration of sensing into a communication system requires an appropriate allocation of the available resources. Also, it may lead to severe interference between sensing and communication, which may degrade the communication performance [61]. To tackle the problem, intelligent reflecting surface (IRS), a low-cost information transmission technology, constitutes a promising approach to facilitate the integration of sensing and communication [62]-[66]. Notably, IRS allows bypassing obstacles, by dynamically creating smart reflections beyond the conventional law of reflection [67]-[71], which is especially beneficial for communication in high frequency bands, such as the millimeter-wave (mmWave) spectrum. Motivated by these considerations, in this article, we analyze IRS-aided ISAC systems in mmWave networks.

Liu et al. [71] studied IRS-assisted multiple-input-single output radio systems with multiple backscatter devices, and they proposed a block coordinate descent algorithm based on Dinkelbach's method to obtain a suboptimal solution, which improves more than two times the system energy efficiency compared with conventional algorithms. The application of IRS to enhance the physical layer security in communication systems is analyzed in [72]-[74]. In nonorthogonal multiple access wireless systems, in addition, IRS has demonstrated major advantages in interference management, coverage enhancement, energy efficiency and spectrum efficiency [75]-[78].

Liu et al. [79] proposed two distinct deployment strategies for radar and communication: 1) separated deployment and 2) shared deployment. In the separated deployment, the radar signal is designed to occupy the null space of the downlink communication channel. In the shared deployment, on the other hand, the beamforming is optimized to satisfy the performance requirements of both radar and communication functions. In [80], an integrated communication and radar system is considered, where a base station (BS) and a multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) radar are combined, to simultaneously provide communication services and detect multiple targets. Wang et al. [81] investigated the integration of active and nearly passive

beamforming techniques in IRS-assisted radar and communication systems to mitigate multiuser interference. Aerial IRS for improving the security in ISAC systems is investigated in [82]. Therein, the authors analyzed the performance of secure transmission in jamming environments by optimizing the deployment of IRS over the air. Due to the blockage of the direct communication link, a distributed semi-passive IRS is deployed in [83] for location sensing and data transmission. Simulation results showed that the deployment of IRS can enable position-sensing solutions offering millimeter-level accuracy. Interested readers are referred to the recent comprehensive survey on IRS for ISAC in [84], for more information on the state of research in this field.

In this work, we investigate an IRS-aided ISAC system in an mmWave multiuser downlink scenario. The main contributions of this article are summarized as follows:

- 1) In an IRS-assisted ISAC system in the mmWave band, the radar subsystem is used to sense the targets of interest, while the communication subsystem provides high-speed communication services to users. The IRS is deployed to simplify the design of BS beamforming and consequently to improve the performance of the communication subsystem.
- 2) We consider the problem of minimizing the beampattern error between the designed and desired beampatterns while maximizing the sum transmission rate, subject to constraints on the communication beamforming vector and the IRS phase shifts. The tight coupling among the optimization variables makes the formulated problem nonconvex. To tackle this problem and develop a computationally efficient solution, we decompose the original problem into two subproblems that can be solved separately.
- 3) Since the desired radar beampattern is influenced by the radar signal covariance (RSC) matrix, we compute a closed-form solution for the RSC matrix by relaxing certain constraints in the first subproblem. Additionally, the quadratic transformation (QT) technique is adopted for the second subproblem. The alternating optimization (AO) algorithm is utilized to obtain efficient solutions for the beamforming vector and the phase shifts of the IRS. Specifically, the phase shifts of the IRS are obtained by the majorization minimization (MM) and the complex circle manifold (CCM) algorithms.

3.4.1 System model and proposed algorithms

As depicted in the following figure, an IRS-assisted ISAC system is studied, which consists of a BS featuring M radar antennas and N communication antennas, serving K single-antenna users. The transmission of statistically independent communication and radar signals is achieved through the utilization of a uniform linear array (ULA) at the BS, enabling the system to simultaneously detect targets and transmit data to K users. The IRS is composed of L reflecting elements, and $\Phi = \text{diag}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_L)$ denotes the diagonal phase shift matrix, where $\varphi_l = \exp(j\theta_l)$ represents the phase shift of the l th reflecting element.

Figure 27: Considered system model

- 1 We consider a separated antenna layout to achieve sensing and communication simultaneously, and two independent but related optimization problems are formulated. An ideal radar beampattern can be obtained before designing the IRS phase shifts and the beamforming of the communication subsystem. First, the optimization of the beampattern can be formulated as a constrained least-squares problem. Then, we proceed to design the communication beamforming and IRS design to enhance the transmission rate and suppress the interference from the radar system to the users.

The proposed algorithms are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. MM and CCM Algorithms.

Algorithm 1 MM Algorithm	Algorithm 2 CCM Algorithm
<p>initialization: A feasible solution $\theta^{(0)}$ and $m = 0$.</p> <p>repeat</p> <p>Obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{(m)} = (\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{E})\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{E})(\theta^{(m)})^H + \mathbf{g}$.</p> <p>Obtain the optimal phase shifts $\theta^{opt(m)}$ in the m iteration</p> <p>Update $\tilde{\theta}^{(m+1)} = \theta^{opt(m)}$ and calculate $f_7(\theta^{(m+1)})$.</p> <p>Set $m \leftarrow m + 1$.</p> <p>until convergence</p>	<p>initialization: $i = 0$, and a feasible solution $\theta^{(0)}$.</p> <p>repeat</p> <p>Obtain the search direction $\mathbf{z}^{(i)}$</p> <p>Obtain the tangent space projection of $\mathbf{z}^{(i)}$</p> <p>Update $\hat{\theta}^{(i)}$ on the tangent space</p> <p>Update $\theta^{(i+1)}$ to the manifold \mathcal{S}^{L+1}</p> <p>Update $i \leftarrow i + 1$.</p> <p>until convergence</p>

3.4.2 Numerical results

In this section, numerical simulations are provided to analyze the performance of the considered IRS-assisted ISAC system. Specifically, the BS is equipped with $M = 4$ radar antennas and $N = 4$ communication antennas. Also, we consider four single-antenna users ($K = 4$), and an IRS equipped with $L = 20$ reflecting elements. The noise power is set to $\sigma^2 = -80$ dBm. Moreover, we consider the presence of three targets positioned at the angles -30° , 0° and 30° . relative to the BS and consider a mesh grid with a 1° step size ranging from -90° to 90° . The following benchmark schemes are considered for comparison with the proposed algorithm. 1) Discrete

Phase Shifts: The phase shifts applied by the IRS are quantized with one bit resolution. 2) Random Phase Shifts: The beamforming vector and the radar RSC matrix are optimized, while the phase shifts of the IRS are randomly generated. 3) Without IRS: The system includes the direct transmission between the ISAC BS and the user without the IRS, and the RSC matrix and the communication beamforming are optimized.

In Figure 28, we characterize the impact of the transmit power for communication P_c on the sum rate.

Figure 28: Sum rate with the transmit power.

The performance of the system is effectively improved as the power increases. The optimized IRS shows the best performance, while the IRS with discrete phase shifts incurs some performance loss because of the quantization error. Additionally, the proposed scheme is superior to the case of IRS with random phase shifts, which validates the benefits of optimizing the phase shifts. Finally, the schemes with the IRS show a significant increase in the sum rate compared to the case without the IRS.

In Figure 29, we depict the influence of the number of IRS reflecting elements L on the sum rate. The sum rate increases with the increment in the number of IRS reflecting elements in all considered schemes. This phenomenon is attributed to the joint optimization of the BS beamforming and IRS phase shifts matrix. As the number of IRS reflecting elements increases, the sum rate obtained with the IRS experiences a substantial enhancement compared to the scheme without the IRS. This enhancement is attributed to the introduction of stronger reflected signals resulting from the increased number of IRS reflecting elements L , thereby enhancing the received power.

Figure 29: Sum rate with the number of IRS elements.

In Figure 30, we illustrate the sum rate as a function of the number of transmit antennas for communication. The utilization of multi-antenna techniques has been extensively validated to enhance communication performance. By employing appropriate beamforming strategies, it is evident that the communication performance is markedly enhanced in all schemes as the number of communication antennas increases from 4 to 16. However, comparing the results with those shown in Fig. 4, it appears to be more cost-effective to increase the number of reflective elements of the IRS to achieve similar gains.

Figure 30: Sum rate with number of antennas.

4 Ray-based ISAC modeling

This section describes the ray tracer, which will be used in INSTICT project’s ISAC performance evaluations. This section also gives some initial results on ISAC sensing of an object. A detailed analysis of the results will be conducted in a future deliverable D1.4.

A common approach in ray tracers have been to use shooting-and-bouncing-ray method (SBR) [90], but this approach has problems with multiple diffraction events. Therefore, a visibility analysis-based path search was selected for investigation in the projects mentioned, which resulted in the method described in [85].

In the following, an overview of the ray tracer is provided. We start by describing the approach used for providing geometrical input for ray tracing. A triangle mesh-based representation is used, which is complemented by a discretization-based modelling, which serves the needs of path computation. In addition, support for composing ray tracing scenes from multiple objects is discussed. Sec. 4.2 describes geometric path computation, which is done with the aid of GPU computation. Sec. 4.3 presents the approach for EM computation and related support. Finally, some numerical results are given.

4.1 Input of geometry

The ray tracer uses triangle mesh-based geometry. A proprietary text file format (named TES) has been specified for this purpose, which includes grouping of triangles to planar walls and annotation of diffraction edges. In addition, named materials are associated with the triangles in the file format.

Restricted use of other file formats is provided by a proprietary tool (named gltf2tes), which is used to convert suitable GLTF files [87] to the TES format. For example, some building geometries available in OpenStreetMap [88] have been saved as GLTF with the aid of Blender software [89] and its OSM add-on. An example is shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31. An example of building data downloaded from OpenStreetMap databases.

The ray tracer relies on discretization of the geometry, where each wall surface is represented by a set of tiles, and similarly diffraction edges are represented by a set of edge segments as illustrated in Figure 32. Centroid points of tiles and edge segments are used in the analysis, which determines line-of-sight visibility for each pair of points. From the viewpoint of path computations, parameters controlling the tile and edge segment sizes are important.

Figure 32. Elements of TES geometry and its relationship to discretization elements.

Moreover, transmitter/receiver antennas (and RIS devices too) are represented as points, and information about the points stored along with associated geometry discretization. An example is shown in Figure 33. JSON files (referred as PTF) are used to store discretization information (tiles, edge segments, Tx/Rx points).

Components for the specification of ray tracing geometry are provided by TES and PTF files. Another JSON file format named GDI is used to define compositions to which ray tracing is applied. A GDI file provides a list of objects, which refer to TES and PTF files. Then, a description of the instantiation of those objects for one or more compositions is provided (Figure 34). An instantiation specified mappings of the objects to the world coordinate frame (WCF) using six parameters to define object position and orientation (rotation).

Figure 33. An example of discretization applied to a triangle mesh approximation of a region in Oulu. Tile-based representation can be seen from the ground area. The grid of red points shows RX points defined for the computation of a coverage map.

Figure 34. A GDI file specifies one or more compositions of the scene. An instance of an object can be static, which means that its location is fixed for all compositions, or dynamic, which means that its location varies over compositions.

4.2 Geometric path tracing

In geometric path computation, propagation paths between selected Tx/Rx point pairs are computed according to the laws of reflection, diffraction and refraction. The ray tracer supports path computation for chains of reflection and diffraction using a two-step approach [85]. In the first step, which is called *route search*, candidate geometric element sequences are determined using a two-level discretization-based visibility analysis. This is based on the ideas presented in [86]. In the second step, called *path refinement*, the intermediate points on the candidate paths are refined to obtain shortest-length optical paths, which are validated in the last step. Basically, this makes up a hybrid ray tracing method [90], where shoot-and-bounce ray tracing (SBR) as the first step is substituted by an environment-driven approach described in [86].

Essential parameters in the path tracing include the maximum number of interactions allowed for the path. A specific limit is provided also for the number of diffractions. In earlier work, these values have been limited to a maximum of 4 interactions and 2 diffractions. To speed up computations, even lower values are typically preferred.

For simulation of diffuse scattering, tile-based discretization must be done for the geometry to establish scatter points. Then, to support EM computation, a two-step approach must be used to trace paths from Tx to scatter points and from scatter points to Rx. In this way, paths containing a single scatter point can be supported for EM computation. Simulation of multiple scatter points on the path is not feasible¹.

Each path in the output of geometric path tracing is described by

- propagation delay (τ_i)
- angle of departure (AoD, $\Omega_{T,i} = (\theta_{T,i}, \varphi_{T,i})$)
- angle of arrival (AoA, $\Omega_{R,i} = (\theta_{R,i}, \varphi_{R,i})$)
- interaction points, each described by
 - interaction type (reflection/diffraction),
 - associated geometry element (wall/edge index)
 - coordinates of the point (x, y, z in WCF)

The output is stored using a proprietary JSON format.

¹ Computational complexity of such implementation would be high. In some tools, scattering is allowed to be the last interaction on the path.

4.3 EM computation

4.3.1 Principle

When a set of N geometric paths have been obtained to model the link between Tx and Rx antennas, the task of EM computation is to obtain channel impulse response (CIR)[93]

$$h(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \delta(\tau - \tau_i),$$

where $a_i \in \mathbb{C}$ are the path coefficients. Corresponding baseband CIR is [93]

$$h_b(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i e^{-j\omega_c \tau_i} \delta(\tau - \tau_i).$$

As described in Sionna documentation [92], the path coefficients a_i are given by

$$a_i = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \mathbf{C}_R^H(\Omega_{R,i}) \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{C}_T(\Omega_{T,i}),$$

where \mathbf{T}_i is a 2×2 transfer matrix that encodes the effect of path on wave strength and polarization², and $\mathbf{C}_T, \mathbf{C}_R: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$ denote the antenna patterns of Tx and Rx antennas, respectively. Coefficients in the transfer matrices and antenna patterns are based on the use of local ray-based basis vectors. For a path with K interactions, the transfer matrix is computed as a product $\mathbf{T}_i = \mathbf{T}_{i,K} \mathbf{T}_{i,K-1} \cdots \mathbf{T}_{i,1} \mathbf{T}_{i,0}$, where $\mathbf{T}_{i,0}$ corresponds to the emission from the source point to the first interaction point (or destination point, if $K = 0$).

From this we can extract three possible tasks:

- (1) path modelling involving computation of \mathbf{T}_i ,
- (2) computing electric field vectors at the receiver point $\mathbf{E}_i = \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{C}_T(\Omega_{T,i})$, and
- (3) computing path coefficients a_i .

For example, if we consider modelling of the wave propagation via RIS, we will perform path modelling for Tx-RIS and RIS-Rx links. Adding Tx antenna pattern allows us to compute models for the N_I rays arriving to RIS ($\mathbf{E}_i^{\text{in}}; i = 1, \dots, N_I$) and applying the RIS model provides departing ($\mathbf{E}_{i,j}^{\text{out}}; j = 1, \dots, N_j$) for AoDs of N_j RIS-Rx link paths. Then, path coefficients for the Rx would be computed using

$$a_j = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \mathbf{C}_R^H(\Omega_{R,j}) \mathbf{T}_j \mathbf{E}_j^{\text{out}},$$

where $\mathbf{E}_j^{\text{out}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_I} \mathbf{E}_{i,j}^{\text{out}}$. For modelling of diffuse scattering, a similar two-link approach is used, that is, a scatter point S connects links Tx-S and S-Rx.

² The phase shift due to wave propagation not included.

4.3.2 Path modelling

As mentioned above, a single named material is associated with each triangle in TES files. Materials associated with path interaction and associated face normal directions are fetched using interaction point info available in geometric path tracing output.

As usual, modelling reflection is based on Fresnel equations [94]. Diffraction modelling is based on the Uniform Theory of Diffraction (UTD)[95], whose extensions are discussed in [96]–[98]. For diffuse scatter modelling, we use the approach described in is based on the approach outlined in [99],[100]. Especially, we combine the reciprocal model from [100] with the option of using the Lambertian model.

EM modelling requires definition of material parameters, which are outlined in Table 2. Permittivity and conductivity of some common materials is provided in [94].

Table 3. Material modelling parameters.

Parameter	Notes
Frequency	Path loss, material characteristics, diffraction and scattering models.
Complex relative permittivity	Eq. (10) in [94].
Conductivity	Depends on the material absorption as a function of frequency.
Effective roughness	Fixed or dependent on incident angle.
Diffuse scatter lobe model	Controlled by two parameters.
Diffuse scatter lobe shaping	Used in directive and double-lobe models [99],[100].
Diffuse scatter cross-pol leakage	K_x ; e.g., see scatter modelling EM primer of [92].

4.3.3 Antenna simulation

To provide support for simulation with various antenna patterns ($\mathbf{C}: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$; recall Sec. 4.3.1), the ray tracer includes a Matlab package, which specifies a common interface for accessing the pattern. Currently, in addition to simple models like dipole, support for some approaches like interpolation of slices (Figure 35) and using patterns obtained via Satimo StarLab measurements is available.

Figure 35. An example of antenna pattern modelling, where the horizontal and vertical slices (top images) have been interpolated to obtain a 3D antenna pattern (illustrated in two ways in bottom images). Radiation strength information must be complemented with polarization specification.

4.4 Implementation

The ray tracer has been implemented as a combination of binary executables and Matlab scripting. Executables perform the route search and path refinement. For these tasks, NVIDIA's OptiX ray tracing engine [91] is used for the task of determining point visibilities. In addition, path refinement has been implemented as accelerated GPU computations with CUDA [85].

Executables are called from Matlab scripts, which take care of preparing the required input files for ray tracing. After geometric paths have been obtained, subsequent EM calculations are done in Matlab. A use case may involve multiple launches of path computations. For example, simulating a case involving RIS requires modelling of Tx-RIS link and RIS-Rx link, simulation of RIS and simulation of antennas. Therefore, dedicated scripts must be implemented to organize computations. An example is shown in Figure 36.

This simulator also comes with some restrictions. Both computational complexity and memory consumption becomes easily high with ray tracing. When application of the tools is considered,

we must pay attention to complexity of basic geometry, discretization granularity³, and restriction for path interaction counts⁴, for example.

Figure 36. Multiple phases of computation in a RIS scenario. Implementation of ray tracing calculations for particular use case may involve organization to multiple steps, as shown in this figure.

³ For examples, tiles of size 10x10 m² are used in [2] for urban scenarios.

⁴ In experiments, we have restricted the number of interactions on the values less than or equal to 4. The diffraction count has been at most 2.

4.5 On application to use cases of INSTINCT

In [101, Chapter 4], ISAC target modelling using a set of *geometrical scatter centers* is discussed. Considering the ray tracing tool, geometric computation of paths could be based on using scatter centers as Tx/Rx points in ray tracing, similarly to the approach used for RIS devices and diffuse scattering. Implementation of the simulation could involve

1. EM path computation from Tx to Rx (not via target).
2. EM path computation from Tx to target points.
3. EM path computation from target points to Rx.
4. Simulation of target scattering to chain paths calculated in steps 2 and 3.

EM path computation in 1-3 involves geometric path computation and subsequent EM modelling. Then in step 4, having specified Tx radiation, electric field vectors are obtained for each path entering the target points and, according to the target scattering model, they are mapped to the electric field vectors propagated over paths determined in step 3.

Simulation of a RIS can be managed in a similar way, i.e., propagating transmitted wave from Tx to RIS, simulating RIS behavior, and finally propagating the RIS output to Rx. Simulation was implemented in this manner in [102], where a phased array type RIS model was adopted to coverage studies (Figure 37). The model consists of multiple metallic plates, each which are small enough to act as diffuse scatterers, but which can jointly beamform a signal to a desired direction. The model has a physical basis with respect to scattering properties and gives a physically feasible pathloss law of the scattered signal as in e.g. [103]. The model mimics practical implementations, which consist of discretized sub-wavelength sized elements each having a constant phase shift. More information on the RIS model used and simulation done with this can be found in [102].

Figure 37. RIS coverage simulation in reference [3].

4.6 Use Case Examples

A channel simulation for a ISAC use case would typically include a ray tracing simulation of an environment with and without a possibly moving object. Figure 38 shows a section of a corridor in UOULU/CWC. The metallic boxes at positions 1-17 are objects used to simulate sensing of these objects, i.e., we capture impulse responses of a monostatic radar. A comparison with the situation without an object to be sensed is included. The frequency band was not defined for these simulations and the results herein show the results for pure ray tracing without EM calculations.

The simulations are run with 17 different object locations and also without objects to see how the impulse responses change as a results of the moving object. Figure 39 shows the impulse responses for situation without objects, and an object in positions 13 and 14. These positions were chosen since the impulse response shows some visual difference. The majority of the paths remain the same regardless of the object. Hence, it means that the object are tractable. As mentioned above, we do not go into analysis in this report as the analysis of the object and tracking requires signal processing algorithms whereas this report focuses more on development of the tools.

Figure 38: System geometry for indoor ISAC simulations.

- Green dashed line = free space pathloss, blue = paths with no scattering
- Magenta = paths with final interaction point along path modelled as diffuse scattering
- Metal surfaces in the environment that generate strong spikes in channel impulse response
- Moving object metallic – reflection spikes are visible when at Tx

Figure 39: Impulse responses of the simulations in different object locations.

Another example is a simulation of the impulse response between for a NLOS multistatic instance in a urban street intersection shown in Figure 40. In this case the a rectangular object is in LOS of Rx and Tx, but the Tx and Rx are in NLOS to each other. Figure 41 shows the impulse responses of the scenario with and without objects. In particular case the object adds some paths. Without the object, there are 93 paths. With the object there are 144 paths, of which 77 are new and 26 have disappeared because of the object. 67 paths remain the same. Again, this suggests that the object is tractable and it presents itself in number of paths that could be used for tracking, but also identification, depending on the time evolution of the paths. This will also be more deeply investigated in the future.

Adaptation of the ray tracer to INSTINCT use cases must be discussed to implement suitable scripts for simulation and provision of outputs. Overall, the ray tracing shows great potential for analysing the INSTINCT scenarios and use cases in realistic and repeatable simulation environment. This is especially since the ray tracer also supports RISs and in practice any frequency band for which there are material characteristics available.

Figure 40: System geometry for city intersection simulations.

Figure 41: Simulated impulse responses in the city intersection.

5 Conclusions

This report looked into detailed exploration of channel, propagation, and sensing models for ISAC and RIS-assisted ISAC systems. The ISAC is among the focal points of INSTINCT project and this report gathers together the channel models for the ISAC. Through a combination of experimental validation, theoretical modeling, and advanced ray-based simulations, the report has shown the potential of integrating ISAC into next-generation wireless networks. This particularly if we can take aid from RISs. The experimental results showed the capability of pixel-by-pixel beamforming algorithms to shape radiation patterns with high precision, while the theoretical models addressed critical challenges such as mutual coupling and impedance mismatches in RIS architectures.

The integration of RIS into physical layer security frameworks showed promising improvements in secret key generation rates, particularly in static environments where traditional methods struggle. Furthermore, the proposed ISAC-aware data header structure offers a practical solution for embedding sensing capabilities into communication systems without compromising throughput. The ray tracing tools developed and adapted for this work provide a powerful means to simulate complex urban environments, enabling realistic performance evaluations of ISAC systems.

All in all, this work gives a good foundation for future research in and out of INSTINCT in RIS-enhanced ISAC, offering insights that are both theoretically sound and practically applicable. The methodologies and findings presented here will support the design of intelligent, secure, and adaptive wireless systems, paving the way for the realization of ISAC in 6G and beyond systems.

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